

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC-ONLINE CONFERENCE “INNOVATIVE
DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION”

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Abstract: *Recently,innovate technologies are being used to work with more and more children in education.Today,new opportunities are opening up for teachers and new opportunities are opening up as they use them.Innovative activity is a specific type of pedagogical activity. - Identify new methods, forms, means of innovation, technologies used in pedagogical practice, used on the child's identity to develop his abilities.Innovative technologies - In this modern environment, due to the dynamic changes in the personal development of the child, the methods, techniques, learning techniques, educational funds aimed at achieving positive results are aimed at achieving positive results. The use of modern educational technologies provides flexibility in the learning process, increases the cognitive interest of students, enhances creative activity.*

Key words: *Innovation,Education,Research,the modern innovative directions in the development of pedagogical education can be distinguished private innovation theory, developments in the field of personal (private) education, organizational and structural model of education*

Introduction

The country is taking comprehensive measures to increase the role of scientific research in the socio-economic development of the country, as well as to deepen the integration of science with education and industry. Local effective mechanisms for commercialization of developments. The necessary conditions are being created to expand the sources of funding for scientific and scientific-technical activities, to encourage the authors of intellectual property, as well as representatives of the real sector of the economy. Research institutions in 2017 -2021 a comprehensive program of measures to strengthen infrastructure and develop innovative activities is being implemented. At the same time, the results of the analysis show that there are a number of organizational, practical and infrastructural problems in the integration of science and industry, the introduction of scientific and technological developments in all spheres of life of the state and society. In particular:

First, there is a low level of commercialization of the results of practical research, scientific and technical activities of research institutions and scientists of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which allows to develop competitive and based on scientific achievements;

Secondly, there is no coordination in the implementation of the results of scientific and scientific-technical activities, as well as control over the effective use of funds for the

implementation of projects of scientific and technical programs of fundamental, applied and innovative research;

Third, there is no link between research institutes and industry, which ensures the effective introduction of scientific and technological developments in various sectors of the economy and the social sphere – the experimental and design-technological infrastructure;

Fourth, the interaction and cooperation between the institutes of the Academy of Sciences and the real sector of the economy is insufficient;

Fifth, the lack of a mechanism to study and analyze the needs of the country's market for innovative research leads to the development of uncompetitive and unprofitable scientific products.

Materials and methods

Innovative activity in the current context of higher education both content and is directly related to organizational structural restructuring. The basis of these processes has been the rapid development of the theory of pedagogical education in the last three to ten years. (A.A.Abdulina, Ye.V.Bondarevskaya, V.I.Zagvyazinskiy, V.S.Ilin, N.M.Kan-Kalik, V.A. Slastenin and others) among the modern innovative directions in the development of pedagogical education can be distinguished private innovation theory, developments in the field of personal (private) education, organizational and structural model of education, the development of a multi-level system of education. Theoretical foundations of pedagogical innovation have been developed over the last decade. In particular, K.Anglovskiy M.V. Clarin, V.Ya. L.yaudis, M.N.Potawnik, S.D.Polyakov, T.I.Shamova, O.T.Xomeriki, N.R.Yusupbekova, V.A.Slastenin and others in the process of identifying specific aspects of the development of pedagogical professionalism and the process of teaching in higher education. The development of innovative opportunities for teachers remains a topic of research. The concept of individual-oriented education is based on a cultural-historical and activity approach (LSVbigotsky, AALeontev, DBElkonin, EVIlenko, VVDavudov, GPShedrovitsky, AGAsmolov) and today in general methodological terms VVSerikov, VGSukerman, VNZ The work of the Kulikovs is of particular importance. At the organizational and managerial level, this problem was dealt with by M.N. Kostikov, V.A. Boltov. One of the key ideas of this concept is to understand the role and place of subject preparation in pedagogical education, and the main focus is on teaching the subject as a means of developing students. Another idea of this concept is related to the design of forms of learning, in which the educational process is considered as a single process (private learning activity) in which the understanding of the material and research work together is the personal pedagogical position of the future teacher. One of the leading ideas of this concept is to understand the role and place of subject preparation in pedagogical education, and the main focus is on teaching the subject as a means of developing students. Another idea of this concept is related to the design of forms of learning, in which the educational process is considered as a single process (private learning activity) in which the comprehension of material and research work are formed as a personal pedagogical position of the future teacher. The main requirements of this approach are as follows: the individual is the main asset for himself and for others, and the process of transforming the individual as a holistic pedagogical process in higher education. There are new ways and

means in education for teachers and students to effectively carry out the results of pedagogical activity. Now many people have concepts like “interactive technologies and methods”, “innovation”, “multimedia learning materials” and many others. At first glance, the words are complex and unknown, but on the other hand have similar meanings. And the thing is, a modern school at this stage of this education must meet certain requirements. This is mainly related to computers, projectors, i.e. equipment in training offices with information resources. There are a variety of pedagogical innovations in the school and each institute uses its own most “fitsus” or traditional innovative technologies in education - listed below. Positive aspects of innovative technologies in the learning process, Innovative processes in education have advantages:

First, for cognitive activity among students, especially in design, we raised prices.

Second, the use of such exercises creates a more comfortable psychological environment for the student, especially when removing stress during communication with the teacher.

Third, the creative space is open to the child, which leads to an increase in high-quality and fun work.

Fourth, informatization not only motivates students, but also attracts more teachers because of the effectiveness of their work and culture.

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The innovative activity of the teacher On the shoulders of the teacher and especially the class teacher, a lot of educational work is loaded. The innovative activity of the teacher allows to make the learning process better and more versatile. Documentation of commitments provides invaluable assistance in organizing parenting sessions and family collaboration, as reward materials are the result of effective work. To this end, institutions are assembling a curriculum that is essential for high-quality assimilation by students of the curriculum. For students, teachers organize an individual lesson in the initial study of a foreign language, the graduates are prepared in advance. Many learning technologies, innovative technologies allow you to choose the head of the institution. Now that the director himself is solving the overall analysis and evaluation, innovative technologies can help to work effectively and successfully in pedagogical activities. Distinguish the following innovative educational technologies:

Health technologies: The main goal is to develop the ability of a conscious child to health and life, health and its protection, storage and preservation, accumulation of knowledge.

Forms of work: gymnastics (morning gymnastics, finger and dynamic gymnastics); Physical education classes; Sports holidays; Fizkulultminutki in the range of dynamic pauses between classes; Walking.

Project activity: Creating problem-solving activities by students with the teacher. During the work on the project, students become their personal wealth and are firmly established in the global knowledge system around the world. The main goal of the project

is to develop a free creative personality, which is defined by the development tasks and objectives of the development of children's research activities.

History

The Federal Ministry for Atomic Issues was established in 1955, concentrating on research in the peaceful use of nuclear energy. The ministry was renamed in 1962 to Federal Ministry of Scientific Research, with a broader scope; it was renamed again, to Federal Ministry of Education and Science, in 1969. A separate ministry, the Federal Ministry of Research and Technology, was established in 1972. The two Ministries merged in 1994 to form the Federal Ministry for Education, Science, Research and Technology; this title was shortened to Federal Ministry for Education and Research in 1998.

The BMBF currently has eight directorates-general (as at November 2020). These are in addition to the central directorate-general that is responsible for administrative tasks:13),

- Directorate-General 1: Policy Issues and Strategies
- Directorate-General 2: European and International Cooperation in Education and Research
- Directorate-General 3: General Education and Vocational Training; Lifelong Learning
- Directorate-General 4: Higher Education and Research System
- Directorate-General 5: Research for Technological Sovereignty and Innovation
- Directorate-General 6: Life Sciences
- Directorate-General 7: Provision for the Future -Basic Research and Research for Sustainable Development

Each directorate-general consists of one or two subdivisions and 10 to 15 units. The greater part of the subdivisions is located in Bonn, the smaller part in Berlin. The BMBF has around 1000 employees. The head of the BMBF is formed by two parliamentary secretaries and two permanent state secretaries in addition to the minister. The Innovation Nation White Paper sets out how businesses and people in the UK are best placed to benefit from the new opportunities and prosperity created by the demand for innovation. Launching the document the Secretary of State for Innovation, Universities and Skills, John Denham, said: "We must make the UK the best place in the world to run an innovative business or public service, where innovation can flourish across every area of the economy.⁶⁶ We must unlock talent at all levels by investing in skills, research and the exploitation of knowledge" It is the British people who will create a world beating innovation nation and that is ES why we must unlock talent at all RT levels by investing in skills. ER research and the exploitation of ay knowledge." John Denham, Secretary of State for Innovation, Universities and Skills The strategy is the first to focus on innovation policy since the creation of the Department for Innovation, Universities and Skills (Dius) and addresses some of the themes raised by Lord Sainsbury in his review of the government's science and innovation policies in October 2007.

Key features include:

- At least 1,000 innovation vouchers every year by 2011 to support small and medium sized businesses to work with a university, further education college or research organisation of their choice

- Doubling the number of knowledge transfer partnerships between businesses, universities and colleges

- Piloting a new specialisation and innovation fund to boost the capacity of further education colleges to unlock workforce talent and support businesses
- Expanding the network of national skills academies.

The shadow secretary of state David Willetts said the measures were a step in the right direction, but would only scratch the surface of the skills shortage. He said: "The Sainsbury Review was an indictment of government failure on innovation and this White Paper is an open admission of guilt. These belated announcements are useful, but they fail to rise to the scale of the challenge." The government still hasn't resolved issues around intellectual property or the skills gap in the economy. "Meanwhile, ministers have been raiding departmental R&D (research and development) budgets to plug gaps in the public finances." Innovation 'stifled' The Association for Science Education welcomed the White Paper, but said innovation was being stifled in school science lessons. The association's Alan Rhodes said: "Our curriculum is so test orientated that children are being taught to pass tests and you do not innovate when teaching children to pass tests." "I believe in high standards, but there is insufficient time for creativity in the curriculum from primary school up to the age of 18." Mr Rhodes heaps praise on the Nuffield Foundation for its "innovative" approach in forging partnerships between education and industry. The Foundation provides independent funding for research and development in education, law, science and social policy. You do not innovate when teaching children to pass tests 99 Alan Rhodes, Association for Science Education.

Conclusion

In the XXI century, which is considered to be the age of information and advanced technologies, the issue of widespread introduction of innovations in the educational process has received more and more attention. In Uzbekistan, in recent years, innovation has been one of the first to enter the education system than in other areas, and we can see how innovation is reflected in the educational process. The introduction of innovation into the system of pedagogical sciences includes the following in the structure of pedagogical sciences:

a) Gender pedagogy;

b) Heuristic pedagogy;

c) Compulsory pedagogy;

d) was marked by the influx of disciplines such as androgogic pedagogy. We can see the introduction of innovations in the education system in the content of education, teaching methods, forms of teaching, types of teaching, teaching aids.

- Innovation in the content of education is explained by the introduction of traditional, non-traditional and distance learning.

- We see the introduction of active, passive and interactive methods of innovation in teaching methods. While the use of the active method serves to increase the activity of

students in the classroom, the passive method is explained by giving students a one-sided understanding. The interactive method is understood to be an active collaboration (teacher with student, student with student). The process of innovation consists of a system of structures and laws. process at the level of world standards based on the achievements of modern pedagogy and psychology.

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